

Boiling Water Reactor Fuel Concept Enabling Efficient Utilization of Plutonium to Reduce Uranium Consumption

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ABSTRACT

In response to rising uranium prices caused by supply-demand imbalances, we developed a new boiling water reactor (BWR) fuel concept, referred to as plutonium effective utilization fuel, to reduce uranium consumption. The plutonium effective utilization fuel was designed to suppress the increase in Pu-240 and decrease in fissile plutonium during operation. This enables maintaining reactivity while reducing plutonium loading. The goal is to increase the energy generated by plutonium recovered from reprocessing and decrease uranium consumption. The plutonium effective utilization fuel suppresses the change in the plutonium isotopic ratio by adding gadolinium to mixed oxide (MOX) fuel rods. By mixing plutonium and gadolinium in the same fuel rod, the increase in Pu-240 during operation is effectively suppressed, and the decrease in fissile plutonium during operation is also suppressed. This is because of the differences in the neutron absorption cross sections between Pu-239 and Pu-240. The Pu-240 neutron absorption reaction has a prominent resonance peak around 1 eV, which is larger than the cross section of gadolinium. In the presence of gadolinium, therefore, the Pu-240 (n, γ) Pu-241 reaction is less suppressed compared with the Pu-239 (n, γ) Pu-240 and Pu-239 fission reactions. Thus, the increase in Pu-240 and decrease in fissile plutonium are mitigated. Compared with conventional MOX fuel, the plutonium effective utilization fuel can suppresses the change in the plutonium isotopic ratio by the gadolinium effect and increase energy generation by plutonium. This enables a 10% reduction in uranium consumption compared with the conventional MOX fuel.

Keywords: MOX fuel, BWR, fuel cycle, gadolinium, plutonium

1. INTRODUCTION

With the growing demand for nuclear power generation, it was declared at COP28 that the capacity of nuclear power will triple by 2050 compared with 2020, [1], and the importance of nuclear energy was reaffirmed at COP29 [2]. However, this increasing demand can cause higher uranium prices. For this study, we addressed the increase in uranium prices is addressed by reducing uranium consumption in light water reactors (LWRs).

Japan has adopted a nuclear fuel cycle policy that involves reprocessing spent fuel and recovering plutonium contained in the spent fuel. Until the transition to a fast reactor cycle, this recovered plutonium is fabricated into mixed oxide (MOX) fuel and used in LWRs. We aimed to reduce uranium consumption by making more effective use of plutonium. To achieve this, we developed a BWR fuel concept referred to as plutonium effective utilization fuel. The plutonium effective utilization fuel enables maintaining reactivity with a reduced plutonium loading. This allows for more electricity generated from plutonium to be increased, reducing uranium consumption in LWRs.

We formulated our fuel and evaluated its uranium-saving effect.

2. CONCEPT OF THE PLUTONIUM EFFECTIVE UTILIZATION FUEL

One of the key challenges in using plutonium in LWRs is the decrease in reactivity caused by the neutron absorption of Pu-240, a non-fissile isotope. For a typical composition of plutonium recovered from reprocessing, the ratio of absorption to production reaction rates in MOX fuel is about 20% higher than that in uranium fuel under conditions where the same amount of fissile isotopes is loaded. The isotopic ratio of Pu-240 also increases during operation because Pu-239 captures a neutron and transforms into Pu-240. Therefore, the effects of Pu-240 becomes more significant towards the end-of-cycle (EOC).

In the plutonium effective utilization fuel, the effects of Pu-240 absorption is reduced by suppressing the increase in Pu-240 during operation. We used gadolinium, which is used as a burnable poison in fuel, for this purpose. The neutron absorption microscopic cross section of the gadolinium isotope Gd-157 is shown in *Figure 1* along with the those of Pu-239 and Pu-240 [3]. This cross section of Pu-239 is smaller than that of gadolinium at the thermal neutron peak in LWRs, while this cross section of Pu-240 has a resonance peak around 1 eV, which is larger than that of gadolinium. Therefore, by adding gadolinium into MOX fuel rods and mixing plutonium and gadolinium to the same fuel rod, the production of Pu-240 via Pu-239 neutron capture and Pu-239 fission is suppressed, and the production of Pu-241 via neutron capture by Pu-240 is relatively promoted. This suggests that the isotopic ratio of Pu-240 can be reduced at the EOC. At the same time, the decrease in Pu-239 is suppressed, and the production of Pu-241 is promoted, which is expected to preserve the fissile plutonium isotopic ratio at the EOC.

Hereafter, a MOX fuel rod with added gadolinium is referred to as a MOX-Gd fuel rod.

In boiling water reactor (BWR) fuel, gadolinium needs to be added to suppress excess reactivity during the early part of the cycle. In this fuel design, MOX-Gd rods are used as burnable poison-containing fuel to control this excess reactivity. This approach enables the utilization of excess reactivity in the early cycle for improving the plutonium isotopic ratio.

Figure 1 Neutron absorption micro cross sections of gadolinium and plutonium in JENDL-5 [3]

2.1. Methodology for evaluating the effects of gadolinium

We first evaluated the effect of gadolinium for improving the plutonium isotopic ratio at the EOC through calculations in an infinite lattice system. We used the BWR 10×10 lattice uranium fuel design with an average discharge burnup of 50 GWd/t, cycle length of 24 months, and bundle average U-235 enrichment of 4.56 wt% as a reference and replaced a uranium fuel rod containing 4.9 wt% U-235 with MOX-Gd fuel rod. The gadolinium effect of improving the plutonium isotopic ratio at the EOC was evaluated by comparing it with the design using MOX fuel rods instead. The plutonium content of MOX-Gd fuel rods was set to 9.3 wt% so that the reactivity at the core-average burnup at the EOC matches that of the reference. These fuel designs are shown in *Figure 2*.

For the calculations in an infinite lattice system, we used VMONT, a multi-group Monte Carlo code [4] [5]. The in-channel void fraction was set to 40% for both historical and instantaneous values, which is core average during rated power operation of BWR. The MOX-Gd fuel rod is modeled by dividing the radial direction into eight regions. The initial plutonium isotopic ratio assumed for fuel property evaluations is shown in *Table 1*. It was assumed that plutonium recovered from spent uranium fuel with a discharge burnup of 45 GWd/t from both pressurized water reactors (PWRs), and BWRs was mixed in a 1:1 weight ratio [6]. The cooling time was set to 30 years, which corresponds to the average storage period for spent fuel to be reprocessed at the Rokkasho Reprocessing Plant (RRP) [7].

Fuel number	U-235 enrichment (wt%)	Plutonium contents (wt%)	Gadolinium contents (wt%)
1	4.9	0.0	0.0
2	3.9	0.0	0.0
3	2.8	0.0	0.0
4	0.2	9.3	10.0
5	0.2	9.3	0.0

Figure 2 Fuel assemblies designed to evaluate the effect of gadolinium.

Table 1. Initial plutonium isotopic ratio

Nuclide	Weight ratio (wt%)
Pu-238	2.3
Pu-239	58.0
Pu-240	27.6
Pu-241	3.4
Pu-242	8.3
Am-241	0.4

2.2. Results of evaluating the effects of gadolinium

The results of evaluating the relationship between the existence of gadolinium and plutonium isotopic ratio during fuel burnup are respectively shown in *Figures 3 (a)* through *(d)*.

As shown in *Figure 3 (a)*, the increase in Pu-240 during operation was suppressed in the MOX-Gd fuel rod. This is because the presence of gadolinium suppresses the $\text{Pu-239}(n, \gamma)\text{Pu-240}$ reaction, reducing the production of Pu-240, while the $\text{Pu-240}(n, \gamma)\text{Pu-241}$ reaction in the resonance region continues to occur, maintaining the decrease in Pu-240. As shown in *Figure 3 (b)* and *(c)*, the decrease in fissile plutonium (Pu-239, Pu-241) during operation was effectively suppressed in the MOX-Gd fuel rod. This is because the presence of gadolinium suppresses Pu-239 decrease by $\text{Pu-239}(n, \gamma)\text{Pu-240}$ while maintaining Pu-241 production by the $\text{Pu-240}(n, \gamma)\text{Pu-241}$.

After gadolinium is depleted, its effect disappears, and the composition gradually becomes similar to that of the MOX fuel rod. As shown in *Figure 3 (d)*, the isotopic ratio of Pu-241, which decays to Am-241 and becomes a major source of decay heat after discharge, becomes the same with the MOX fuel rod before discharge.

Figure 3 Changes in plutonium isotopic ratio during burnup

3. CORE PROPERTY AND IMPLEMENTATION EFFECTS OF THE PLUTONIUM EFFECTIVE UTILIZATION FUEL

3.1. Designs of the plutonium effective utilization fuel

Based on the concept established in the previous section, the plutonium effective utilization fuel was designed. We evaluated the equilibrium cycle core property by using PANACEA [8]. PANACEA uses a diffusion model in which the three-group equations are reduced to one group by assuming identical geometric buckling for all energy groups (1.5-group model). The design and calculation conditions are respectively listed in *Table 2* and *Table 3*.

Table 2 Design conditions

Items		Conditions
Core	Reactor type	Advanced Boiling Water Reactor (ABWR)
	Thermal power (MW)	3,926
	Core flow (kt/h)	52
	Core pressure (MPa)	7.2
	Bundle average discharge burnup (GWd/t)	50
	Cycle length (month)	24
	Number of fuel bundles	872
	Number of control rods	205
Bundle	Lattice configuration	10×10
	Number of fuel rods	92
	Number of MOX-Gd fuel rods	12
	Bundle average U-235 enrichment (wt%)	3.9
	MOX-Gd plutonium contents (wt%)	9.3
	MOX-Gd gadolinium contents (wt%)	6.5

Table 3 Calculation conditions

Items		Conditions
Method	Code	VMONT/PANACEA
	Number of energy group	190/1.5
	Nuclear data library	JENDL-4.0
Constraints	Maximum linear heat generation rate (KW/m)	≤ 44
	Minium critical power ratio (-)	≥ 1.4 (tentative)
	Shut down margin (%Δk)	≥ 1.5
	Excess reactivity (%Δk)	≥ 0.0

3.2. Results of core property evaluation

The results of the equilibrium cycle core property evaluations are presented in *Table 4*. All design constraints were satisfied, indicating that the plutonium effective utilization fuel is feasible.

Table 4 Evaluation result of the core property

Constraints	Plutonium effective utilization fuel
Maximum linear heat generation rate (KW/m)	38.9
Minium critical power ratio (-)	1.62
Shut down margin (%Δk)	1.6
Excess reactivity (%Δk)	2.6

3.3. Evaluation of uranium-saving effect

The uranium-saving effect of the plutonium effective utilization fuel was evaluated by comparing it with conventional MOX fuel (8×8 MOX fuel). Assuming the current uranium fuel design is used, the amount of natural uranium required in the Japanese BWR fleet is calculated on the basis of Eq. (1). The total heavy metal mass of required uranium fuel was first obtained by dividing the thermal energy generated by uranium fuel. The required amount of natural uranium for fabricating the uranium fuel was then calculated from the heavy metal mass and the enrichment level. The calculation also accounts for the tails assay in the enrichment process. Similarly, the required amount of natural uranium for MOX fuel was calculated using the enrichment level applied to the uranium portion of the MOX fuel. Depleted uranium or recovered uranium used in the base material of MOX fuel rods, which are generated during the enrichment and reprocessing processes, were not included in the uranium weight evaluation, as they are considered unaffected by uranium pricing. The evaluation conditions are shown in *Table 5*. The power generation capacity of the Japanese BWR fleet was set as the BWR generation capacity when nuclear power accounts for 22% of Japanese electricity demand. Plutonium can also be used in the Japanese BWR fleet and was set as half the annually recovered plutonium from the RRP allocated for BWR use.

$$U_{BWR} = \frac{G_{BWR} - G_{MOX}}{B_U} \frac{E_U - E_t}{E_n - E_t} + \frac{G_{MOX}}{B_{MOX}} \frac{E_{MOX} - E_t}{E_n - E_t} \quad (1)$$

$$G_{MOX} = \frac{P_{BWR}}{C_{MOX}} B_{MOX} \quad (2)$$

where,

U_{BWR} : Weight of natural uranium used in BWR (tU)	E_U : Bundle average enrichment of uranium fuel (wt%)
G_{BWR} : Thermal energy generation in BWR (GWd)	E_{MOX} : Bundle average enrichment of MOX fuel (wt%)
G_{MOX} : Thermal energy generated by MOX fuel (GWd)	E_t : Enrichment of tail uranium (wt%)
B_U : Average discharge burnup of uranium fuel (GWd/t)	E_n : Enrichment of natural uranium (wt%)
B_{MOX} : Average discharge burnup of MOX fuel (GWd/t)	C_{MOX} : Bundle plutonium contents of MOX fuel (wt%)
P_{BWR} : Weight of plutonium used in BWR (tPu)	

Table 5 Evaluation conditions for saving of uranium effect

Item	Values
Power generation capacity of Japanese BWR fleet (GWe)	12.2
Plutonium can be used in Japanese BWR fleet (tPu/year)	3.3
Enrichment of tail uranium (wt%)	0.2

The evaluation results are presented in *Table 6*. The cycle length of the plutonium effective utilization fuel was set to 24 months, identical to that of the reference uranium core. To evaluate the 8×8 MOX fuel under the same cycle length, the plutonium content of 8×8 MOX fuel required for a 24-month cycle was estimated using a linear reactivity model. Since the reactivity of MOX fuel is very nearly linear function of burnup, this approximation is considered valid.

Compared with conventional MOX fuel, the plutonium effective utilization fuel increases energy generation by MOX fuel. Therefore, the electricity generated from uranium fuel decreases, enabling a 10% reduction in uranium consumption compared with the conventional MOX fuel Under the assumptions listed in *Table 5*.

Table 6 Results of uranium saving effect evaluation

Fuel type	Plutonium effective utilization fuel	8×8 MOX fuel
Thermal energy generation by MOX fuel (GWd/year)	1838	541
Thermal energy generation by uranium fuel (GWd/year)	11,724	13,021
Weight of natural uranium used in BWR fleet (tU/year)	2,005	2,226
Uranium saving effect (%)	10	Base

4. CONCLUSIONS

We developed the concept of the plutonium effective utilization fuel, which applies gadolinium to control the plutonium isotopic ratio.

By adding gadolinium to MOX fuel rods and mixing plutonium and gadolinium in the same fuel rod, the increase in Pu-240 during operation is effectively suppressed, and the decrease in fissile plutonium during operation is also suppressed. This is because gadolinium suppresses the Pu-239(n, γ)Pu-240 reaction, while the Pu-240(n, γ)Pu-241 reaction in the resonance region continues to occur.

The plutonium effective utilization fuel can improve the plutonium isotopic ratio at the EOC and increase energy generation per unit of plutonium. The evaluation of annual natural uranium usage in the Japanese BWR fleet indicates that the plutonium effective utilization fuel can achieve a 10% reduction compared with 8×8 MOX fuel.

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